

A STUDY ON HR POLICIES AND PRACTICES IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE

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Abstract:

HR Practices refers to process of choosing the best workforce plan an organization to attain a goals or objectives. Good HRM practices are instrumental in helping achieve departmental objectives and enhance productivity. For the purpose of sharing experience and providing reference in launching HRM initiatives, we have gathered in this booklet some good examples introduced by departments. The main objective of the study is to understand the problem in job recruitment process in Textile industry and to analyse the perception of employees on HR practices implemented. For this purpose a sample of 150 was collected from respondents were percentage analysis, descriptive statistics and chi-square were used as tools to analyse the data and the conclusion is that Evaluation and periodic assessment are important for improvement and effectiveness.

Key Words: Employees, Evaluation & Productivity

Introduction to the Concept of the Study:

A HR policy is a formalized human resources document that presents a broad overview of standard operating policies and procedures for an organization. It is an essential document that provides structure and establishes consistency and discipline in decision-making and employee behaviour. HR policy is a booklet or a piece of document that gives the reader a fair idea of the working procedures of the particular company or organization. They give guidelines on how to apply the rules and regulations that a company has set for its functioning. This kind of policy is especially useful for HR officials so that they do not break rules that may lead the company to societal and legal problems. Thus, it is quite evident that an HR policy is of some importance to organizations for smooth functioning. They also need to be reviewed and revised time and again so that the management of the company keeps up with the changing trends and also keep tract of new legal acts that may be enforced upon the working of organizations.

A policy that gives HR policies of an organization along with a wide overview of different HR procedures such as work force planning, enlisting, pay packages and profits, grooming, employee governance, etc. is called an HR manual. It is usually fashioned for internal use in the HR department only. With the development of an establishment, different other appendages could be imbibed into it in order to keep this policy updated HR manuals are complete compilations of policies and procedural corroborations relevant to employees within the organization.

Statement of the Problem:

Employing staff fairly and expertly, ensuring they are properly inducted, and ensuring they are aware of the required standards of business conduct we need an effective HR policy including the policies and procedures of the organization. HR manager finds difficult to search the required information without an effective manual. And also to minimize the time indulged in explaining the policies and procedures of the organizations to the newly employed staff we require an effective HR policy explaining all the methods, policies and procedures of the organization.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the multi various functions of HRM's and their relevance in achieving the targeted textile companies.
- ✓ To analyse the perception of employees on HR practices implemented.
- ✓ To analyse the level of acceptance of employees on HR practices.
- ✓ To suggest about the perception of employees on HR practices implemented.

Scope of the Study:

Today human resources occupy, more than ever, the center stage of all economic activities. It is alarming time for all those organizations that wish to be successful in global markets to gear up and implement desired shift in their prevailing human resource management practices and leverage their human resources along with the other resources. Also to become more flexible and innovative organizations need to adopt new ways of attracting, retaining and motivating employees who are keen to learn and can contribute to the growth and development of the organization. In an increasingly competitive market, survival and prosperity of business will

depend critically on the ways an organization manages its resources especially the human resources. The main scope of the study is that it will be useful for the company to know about the HR practices of the textile companies.

Research Methodology:

Type of Research: The type of research design undertaken is Descriptive Research. Descriptive research includes surveys and fact-findings enquiries of different kinds. The major purpose of descriptive research is description of state of affairs, as it exists at present.

Data Collection Method: The main sources through which data is collected are:

Primary Data: The Primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire from the employees.

Secondary Data: Secondary data was collected from magazines, journals, books and websites.

Sample Design: Sample Design is method of selecting the samples. To collect primary data from 116 samples were selected among the employee in the company. The stratified random sampling method of sampling was applied to select the sample respondents

Tools for Analysis: The Data collected was analyzed using simple percentage analysis, Chi Square and Descriptive statistics.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic Variables:

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	110	73.3
	Female	40	26.7
	Total	150	100
Age	Below 18	5	3.3
	18-25	52	34.7
	26-35	47	31.3
	Above 35	46	30.7
	Total	150	100
Educational Qualification	10th	5	3.3
	Higher Secondary	5	3.3
	UG	82	54.7
	PG	53	35.3
	Others	5	3.3
Total	150	100	
Place of living	Semi Rural	10	6.7
	Rural	52	34.7
	Urban	74	49.3
	Semi Urban	14	9.3
	Total	150	100
Monthly income	Below 5000/Month	10	6.7
	5000-10000/Month	69	46
	10000-15000/ Month	42	28
	15000-20000	18	12
	Above 20000	11	7.3
	Total	150	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows the demographic variables of the respondents were out of 150 respondents 73.3% are male and 26.7% are female. 3.3% are form the age group of below 18, 34.7% are from the age group of 18-25, 31.3% are form the age group of 26-35, and 30.7% are from the age group of above 35. 3.3% have completed their 10th standard, 3.3% have completed their higher secondary, 54.7% have completed their UG, 35.3% have completed their PG and 3.3% have completed other courses. 6.7% are from semi rural area, 34.7% are from rural area, 49.3% are from urban area and 9.3% are from semi urban area. 6.7% are earning below 5000 per month, 46% are earning from 5000-10000/month, 28% are earning form 10000-15000/ month, 12% are earning from 15000-20000 and 7.3% are earning above 20000.

Descriptive Statistics:

Descriptive Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Level of satisfaction towards favourable incentive practices to encourage employees to achieve the firm's objectives	150	2.79	0.999	0.997

Level of satisfaction towards structured and standardized interviews used in firm	150	3.07	1.109	1.23
Level of satisfaction towards training programs provided for employees in firm	150	2.87	1.095	1.199
Level of satisfaction towards self-ratings on performance	150	2.67	0.909	0.825
Level of satisfaction schemes provided by the company	150	2.7	0.981	0.963

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the descriptive statistics of factors related to level of satisfaction and the factors above average mean (2.82) are taken in to consideration for decision making process of the study. The factors are level of satisfaction towards structured and standardized interviews used in firm and level of satisfaction towards training programs provided for employees in firm.

Chi Square Analysis:

Educational Qualification and Level of Acceptance of Various Factors Used for the Study:

H0: There is no significant relationship between educational qualification of the respondents and level of acceptance of various factors used for the study.

Demographic Profile	Chi-Square Value	P Value	Result
Level of acceptance towards large number of people involved in HR planning in firm	44.423	0.000	Reject
Level of acceptance towards firm spending a great amount of money on selecting staff	40.312	0.001	Reject
Level of acceptance towards firm forecasting personnel requirements on a timely basis	40.421	0.000	Reject
Level of acceptance towards firm focused groups to solve problems	83.309	0.000	Reject
Level of acceptance towards team's opinion and ideas before making any decision	54.739	0.000	Reject
Level of acceptance towards practice of carrying employee attitude surveys	1.734	0.000	Reject
Level of acceptance towards formal procedure of potential appraisal	57.281	0.000	Reject
Level of acceptance towards management style in their company brings out the best in employees	59.852	0.000	Reject
Level of acceptance towards usefulness of team meetings	67.552	0.000	Reject
Level of acceptance towards awareness of the latest policies and schemes that are availed by the government	29.049	0.021	Reject
Level of acceptance towards supportive Government Policies	47.028	0.000	Reject
Level of acceptance towards increased domestic competition	1.346	0.000	Reject
Level of acceptance towards adapting to a host of quality management systems	56.499	0.000	Reject
Level of acceptance towards company finding an un-supportive economic environment	72.863	0.000	Reject

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between educational qualification and level of acceptance of various factors used for the study. It shows that there is a relationship between Educational qualification and all the factors related to level of acceptance as the level of significance is lesser than 0.05 were alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Findings:

- ✓ Most of the respondents are male in our survey.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are from the age group of 18-25.
- ✓ Most of the respondents have completed their UG in our survey.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are from urban area in our survey.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are earning from Rs 5000-10000/month.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are neutral about favourable incentive practices to encourage employees to achieve the firm's objectives.
- ✓ Most of the respondents agree for acceptance towards large number of people involved in HR planning in firm.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents agree for acceptance towards firm spending a great amount of money on selecting staff.
- ✓ Most of the respondents agree for acceptance towards firm forecasting personnel requirements on a timely basis.

- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are satisfied about structured and standardized interviews used in firm.
- ✓ Most of the respondents agree for acceptance towards firm focused groups to solve problems
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents agree for acceptance towards team's opinion and ideas before making any decision.
- ✓ Most of the respondents agree for acceptance towards supportive Government Policies
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents agree for acceptance towards increased domestic competition.
- ✓ Most of the respondents agree for acceptance towards adapting to a host of quality management systems
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents agree for acceptance towards company finding an un-supportive economic environment.
- ✓ There is a relationship between Educational qualification and all the factors related to level of acceptance as the level of significance is lesser than 0.05 were alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Suggestions:

The suggestion scheme is designed with the objective of encouraging creative thinking and suggestions leading to improvements in overall working of the organization. All employees are welcome to contribute their suggestions under this scheme. Suggestions will be contributed in the following areas:

- ✓ Ideas to save time
- ✓ Improving the image of the company
- ✓ Improving quality of service
- ✓ Increasing operational efficiency
- ✓ Improving working conditions
- ✓ Cost reduction
- ✓ Improving productivity, and
- ✓ Improvement in office procedures and methods

All employees who wish to make suggestions will contribute their suggestions in the specified form available with the HR Department. The filled up suggestion form will be deposited in the HR Department.

Communication:

Open and informal communication is an important channel for employee to voice and discuss their problems with the Management. It builds commitment and trust between the employees and the organization.

Personal Communication:

The scheme allows all employees to communicate their problems directly to the ED. They can write to the ED, on the organizational issues, which will be acted upon. This process is expected to give satisfaction to the employees.

ED Meetings:

The ED will conduct formal and informal meetings with the employees from time to time, to discuss organization related issues. The highlighted issues will be taken up by him/ her with the Departmental Head concerned, for follow up on the same for resolution.

HR Audit:

Evaluation and periodic assessment are important for improvement and effectiveness. The company will carry-out audit of the HR policies and procedures. The responsibility of the HR Audit lies with the HOD-HR. The audit will provide a feedback to the Management on the strengths and weaknesses of the system and areas for improvement. It will also provide an opportunity to have a re-look at some of the existing systems and plan for a change. These audits should be conducted once in a year. The audit should cover all areas relating to HR, and Administration.

Conclusion:

Human resource policies are continuing guidelines on the approach the organization intends to adopt in managing its people. It represents specific guidelines to HR managers various matters concerning employments. The main objective of the study is to understand the problem in job recruitment process in textile industry and to analyse the perception of employees on HR practices implemented. The conclusion is that Evaluation and periodic assessment are important for improvement and effectiveness.

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